

The Role Of Nanoinfluencers In Actual Marketing And Other Key Elements

By David Vidal

What are nanoinfluencers?

Short history of social networks

SixDegrees.com was a web-based social networking service launched in 1997⁽¹⁾. It was based on the Web of Contacts model and named after the concept of six degrees of separation⁽²⁾. Users could list people, even if they were not registered on the site. People who confirmed a relationship with an existing user but did not register on the site continued to receive occasional email updates and requests. Users can send messages and post on the bulletin board to people who are their first, second, or third-degree relatives, and view their connection to any other user on the site. The app closed in 2001.

SixDegrees was followed by other social networks such as Friendster, LinkedIn and MySpace in 2001, 2002 and 2003 respectively⁽³⁾. Everything changed in 2008 with the arrival of Facebook, which has led the social networking market from its inception to the present day, with 3 billion active users today⁽⁴⁾. With features such as targeted advertising and sponsored content, Facebook⁽⁵⁾ allows brands to engage with their customers in a more personal way, improving their performance year on year. In addition, Facebook's acquisition of Instagram in 2012 and WhatsApp in 2014⁽⁶⁾ further expanded its influence and diversified its offering, with Instagram appealing to young people and businesses, and WhatsApp giving Facebook the lead in messaging apps.

The Internet is filled with a variety of social networking apps, each with its own features. From the widely used Facebook and its associated platforms, Instagram and WhatsApp, TikTok⁽⁷⁾ for short videos, LinkedIn⁽⁸⁾ for professional networking, X⁽⁹⁾ (formerly Twitter) for real-time news and public discourse, Snapchat⁽¹⁰⁾ for ephemeral messaging and multimedia content, Pinterest⁽¹¹⁾ for creative ideas, and Discord⁽¹²⁾ for real-time communication. Specialised platforms like Reddit⁽¹³⁾, Tumblr⁽¹⁴⁾, and Twitch⁽¹⁵⁾ provide dedicated spaces for content creation, and communities.

As the social media landscape continues to evolve, users can anticipate the emergence of new platforms, offering novel experiences and opportunities for connection in an ever-changing digital world.

Characteristics of influencers

Influencer research is the pursuit of information and verification regarding influencers in order to find a person who is appropriate for the nature and attributes of your brand and promotions⁽¹⁶⁾.

The first step is to create a short list of possible influencers that should be considered initially. Once you have a short list of potential candidates that you think fit the campaign, the next step in influencer research is digging into them and understand what they can accomplish. This is the step where you must be aware of the traits of influencers that you need for your campaign.

Reach

“Reach” refers to the total number of unique users or accounts exposed to a particular piece of content⁽¹⁷⁾. It quantifies the potential size of the audience that an influencer can reach with their posts across various social media platforms.

To calculate the reach efficiency rate of a particular influencer, use the following equation:

$$\text{Reach Efficiency Rate} = (\text{AVG. Reach} / \# \text{ of followers}) \times 100^{(18)}$$

Calculating the reach efficiency rate will allow you to maximise your business’ ROI as – usually – the more followers an influencer has, the more you will have to spend to get them to promote your product or service.

Relevance

Of course, your influencers need to be relevant⁽¹⁹⁾. Relevance is not a precise and measurable metric, but rather a judgement call. Influencers tend to be interested in lots of different things, to varying degrees, and their audience’s preferences can only be inferred.

Use the influencer research sheet in the template to record and assess the relevance of each influencer. Look for Hashtags/ Topics and Unique Facts or Interests that the influencer and your brand, product or organisation have in common.

Relevance	
Hashtags / Topics	Unique Facts or Interests
#tech #technology #marketing #socialmedia	Lives in Ireland, travels, loves sailing, vegan food, playing drums & guitar

Relevance is vital for attracting people who belong to your target group⁽²⁰⁾. Before carrying out your research, you should have in mind that the influencer must have similar characteristics or at least be appealing to your buyer persona, and of course, shares content relevant to your industry. Additionally, you should take into account demographic characteristics such as age and gender.

Resonance

Always looking for influencers who apply the KISS concept ⁽²¹⁾: Keep it Significant and Shareable. Resonance is referred to as something "going viral". Those objects incentivized by thoughtfulness, value, and perhaps even empathy, will gain traction and encourage response and sharing, transitioning from relevance to resonance. And, the ingredients for resonance are readily available for those businesses that pay close attention to the recurring themes in customer conversations, actions, and reactions.

Buddy Media Group, a social media agency based in London, redefined in 2012 the term KISS in this list of tricks⁽²²⁾ to have your content shared more frequently:

- *Keep it short, stupid!* That's right, posts of 80 characters or less get 23% more social interactions (comments, likes, shares) than the average.
- A post featuring a photo will get 39% more interactions than a text-only on Facebook.
- Asking a question in a post gets you 15% more interaction. And placing the question at the end of the post, rather than at the beginning, will yield twice the results.
- Asking fans to complete a sentence or fill in the blank gets 5.5 times more comments than the average post.
- Using emoticons works 😊. In fact, it increases interactions by 52% by helping humanizing the brand, giving it a tone and manner (unless you abuse it, of course).
- Last but not least: ask people to share! Every now and then, it's OK to ask your followers or fans to share a specific tweet or post, whether it's for a contest, special offer or great cause your brand is associated with.

Engagement Ratio

Because nano and micro-influencers have a much more intimate audience than macro-influencers do, they often see a higher engagement rate⁽²³⁾. This means that their posts are reaching a higher percentage of their followers and a lot more of the people seeing their content are actually engaging with it (i.e., liking, commenting, sharing).

One study⁽²⁴⁾ found that micro-influencers see a 6% engagement rate on Instagram, while mega-influencers see engagement rates around 1.97%.

Follower / Following Ratio

It's thought that your follow ratio gives people a quick idea of how "cool" your account is. That's because popular accounts tend to have far more accounts following them than vice versa⁽²⁵⁾.

Your follower ratio is also a general indication of:

- how popular your content is
- how selective you are with your follows
- how likely you are to follow back

Follow Ratio = Number of Followers ÷ Number of Accounts Followed

You can use the following general benchmarks to get an idea of account quality⁽²⁶⁾:

- **< 0.5 = Spam:** Brands who follow twice as many accounts as accounts that follow them are likely trying to gain followers by follow-back schemes.
- **0.5 - 1 = Low Quality:** This ratio doesn't scream spam, but it also doesn't indicate a must-follow account.
- **1 : 2 = Average:** A slightly positive follow ratio is indicative of a new, yet growing account.
- **2 : 10 = Quality:** An account in this range has proven they are worth a follow.
- **10 : 300,000+ = Influencer:** An account in this range easily gains new followers and has a major influence on their social media sphere.

Relevance of nanoinfluencers in the digital world

As influencer marketing continues to evolve, the role of nano influencers is expected to grow⁽²⁷⁾. Brands are recognizing the value of authenticity and personal connections in their marketing strategies. The future may see an increased integration of nano influencers in broader marketing plans, with brands leveraging their unique ability to connect with audiences.

Rather than viewing nanoinfluencers in isolation, brands are likely to incorporate them as integral parts of their marketing strategies⁽²⁸⁾. Combining nanoinfluencers with other marketing channels, such as collaborations with industry experts or traditional advertising, can create a comprehensive approach that maximises reach and impact. The rise of nano influencers reflects a broader shift towards valuing quality over quantity in the digital marketing landscape.

In conclusion, the landscape of influencer marketing is undergoing a transformative shift, and nano influencers are emerging as catalysts for authentic brand connections in the digital realm. As brands navigate this landscape, recognizing the power of personal connections fostered by nano influencers becomes increasingly evident. Their ability to engage smaller but highly engaged audiences brings a depth to marketing strategies that larger influencers may struggle to achieve.

The impact of nanoinfluencers

Importance of influencer marketing

TikTok has become mainstream; podcasts are part of our daily routines; Instagram is now video-first and shopping-oriented. And, wherever possible, consumers opt-out of advertising. We have arrived in a new era of democratic media consumption where consumers choose what they listen to and who they trust⁽²⁹⁾.

Gen Z (a demographic aged 16-26) now makes up 40% of consumers⁽³⁰⁾. They are the most “plugged in” generation to date, spending three hours every day on social media consuming and creating content, and most importantly, seeking inspiration. The pandemic has shown that more mature audiences increasingly mimic this behaviour, meaning that a comprehensive online offering is no longer optional.

The 7 benefits⁽³¹⁾ of Influencer Marketing are:

- Influencer marketing has the second highest ROI (Return Of Investment) of any marketing trend.
- Due to this high ROI, influencers help you save money in your marketing campaigns.
- Influencers are more trusted than friends and family for Gen Zers.
- Influencers help you establish social proof and build awareness.
- Influencers inspire purchases; 33% of Gen Zers have bought a product based on an influencer's recommendation in the past three months.
- You can establish long-term relationships.
- Influencers help you share authentic content in a human way.

Influencer marketing doesn't just get you in front of the audience you're trying to reach — it gets you there in a way that feels authentic and human. As consumers have moved away from sales to drive leads-type ads and more humanised content, a recommendation from a trusted influencer helps you inspire sales by building upon a pre-existing relationship.

4 typical benefits nano-influencers offer that are HUGE wins for brands

- 1** Great engagement ratios
- 2** Street cred... Nano-influencers tend to be more in tune with their audiences, which makes them more authentic
- 3** Affordability... Nano-influencers often the most cost-effective option for brands that want to reach targeted audiences
- 4** Value... Nano-influencers often over-deliver on their contracts

How they influence purchase decisions

It is known that nanoinfluencers are capable of bringing about a considerable effect on sales due to the connection that they manage to build with their followers⁽³²⁾, who believe them on a level of trust. It is worth mentioning that unlike macro and even micro-influencers, nanoinfluencers usually work with fewer yet more actively involved audiences consisting of friends, relatives, and people from their own communities. This stronger bond empowers nanoinfluencers to sway their followers' buying habits with authentic suggestions and stories related to personal experience.

At times, nanoinfluencers use products and services in their day-to-day life to present them so subtly that they become part of their content and blend naturally⁽³³⁾. By being authentic, they not only build a relationship of trust but also make people feel close to them so that they see these people as honest individuals and not paid agents. Consequently, when nanoinfluencers suggest a product or narrate their successful story, their followers are more inclined to take it up on its merit.

One key advantage that nanoinfluencers hold over their macro counterparts is that they usually know better about the audience's tastes, interests, and real issues, thus making sure their content and recommendations are aligned with what followers want or need. By focusing on such issues and delivering valuable information, nanoinfluencers may succeed in positively influencing their followers' decision-making process when it comes to buying goods.

Moreover, nanoinfluencers normally create an atmosphere of togetherness and involvement with their content, promoting discussion and getting feedback from their followers⁽³⁴⁾. The active role of these participants makes the bond between nanoinfluencers and the audience more powerful, increasing the impact of their opinions.

In conclusion, nanoinfluencers have a significant part to play in the process of forming purchase decisions by using their genuineness, connections to the target audience, and recommending products that they themselves used or services as a result of this relationship.

Examples of successful campaigns

One of **Daniel Wellington's**⁽³⁵⁾ promotional strategies was their **#DWPickoftheDay**⁽³⁶⁾ campaign, where they collaborated with some nano influencers to showcase their watches. They encouraged their followers to share selfies with the Daniel Wellington watches by using the hashtag #DWPickoftheDay. The campaign resulted in a significant amount of user-generated content and social proof, raising awareness about the brand and increasing engagement across all key social media channels.

A nanoinfluencer's use of Glossier **Generation G Lipstick**⁽³⁷⁾. Glossier, a cosmetics brand, utilised nanoinfluencers for their marketing campaign. They sent custom lipstick shades to nanoinfluencers with a small but engaged following. These influencers then produced authentic content featuring the lipsticks and shared their honest reviews with their followers. This grassroots approach enabled Glossier to target a specific audience that would value these products, leading to a boost in sales through organic recommendations.

The clothing retailer **Old Navy**⁽³⁸⁾ has recently come up with an interesting initiative of a campaign called **#SayHi**⁽³⁹⁾ to popularise their new back-to-school collection. The company successfully involved nano-influencers, most of which were parents and students, to develop and share interesting content regarding the brand's latest range of clothes. As these influencers relayed their shopping experiences as well as style tips or any other special pieces they found, this brought life into Old Navy's back-to-school collection and generated strong interest among consumers in it.

The influencer partnerships of **FitTea**⁽⁴⁰⁾: The health and wellness brand, FitTea, has launched its products through a network of nano-influencers to promote their detox teas. Their effort included the gift of free samples as well as individualised discount codes for sharing with influencers' followers. These nano-influencers provided FitTea an audience through relatable stories, visual evidence such as before and after photos, and lifestyle content resulting in increased awareness and conversions, especially among health-seeking consumers.

Working with nanoinfluencers

Collaboration strategies

Collaborating with nanoinfluencers requires a tailored approach to leverage their authenticity and engagement effectively⁽⁴¹⁾. Here are some collaboration strategies with nanoinfluencers:

Identify Relevant Nanoinfluencers: In your study, make sure you fully explore the world of nanoinfluencers in order to pinpoint those who would be best aligned with your brand's values, interests, and target audience. You can search for those people who have a direct connection with the market you are in and whose followers are highly interested and interact positively.

Build Authentic Relationships: First, before choosing the nanoinfluencer, reach out and start communication in a personalised and genuine way. Try to dedicate time to following their content, building a friendship with them, and expressing your wish for cooperation. The key to successful cooperation is the creation of trustworthy and respectful relations that are built on trust.

Offer Value: It is necessary to give nanoinfluencers appropriate incentives that reflect their interests and the target audience. This might include promotional discounts on new product ranges, freebies, or special access to events, experiences, etc. Ensure your offerings correspond well with the influencer's taste as well as with the expectations of their audience.

Encourage Creativity and Authenticity: Regarding creative freedoms, it is better to give nanoinfluencers the possibility to develop their content through which they will be able to reveal their real voice and style.

Facilitate User-Generated Content: The development of the industry includes and must consist not only of dull scripted and promotional material but also of fascinating storytelling and sincere recommendations that resonate with their target group.

Leverage Micro-Communities: Let nanoinfluencers generate user-generated content that speaks of your brand in an authentic way. Such content can include product reviews, unboxing videos, behind-the-scenes photos or videos, or even day-in-the-life posts. User-generated content is a trusted source of trust and credibility for the followers of the influencer.

Track and Measure Performance: Sometimes, micro-communities that nanoinfluencers form around their followers all have similar interests and passions. In your collaboration with nanoinfluencers, you can organise virtual events, workshops, or Q&A sessions that would contribute to interaction and engagement among these micro-communities.

Establishing well-defined goals and metrics like Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)⁽⁴²⁾ will guide you in your collaboration with nanoinfluencers.

Tools to identify them

An influencer marketing tool is software that helps marketers find, engage with and make deals with influencers in their niche⁽⁴³⁾. This software includes filtering influencers based on certain characteristics, sending pre-written email pitches and finding online conversations about your brand.

Influencer marketing tools for social listening

Brandwatch: Brandwatch⁽⁴⁴⁾ is a consumer research platform that helps marketers understand their audience, track conversations and monitor brand mentions. You can use it across multiple online channels to keep an eye on specific keywords, phrases and hashtags.

Traackr: Traackr⁽⁴⁵⁾ provides detailed insights into the demographics, interests and behaviour of influencers' audiences. While this feature is primarily designed to help brands understand the characteristics of an influencer's audience, it can also provide indirect insights into broader social media conversations and trends by analysing the interests and engagement patterns of the influencer's followers.

Influencer marketing tools for identification

Heepsy: Heepsy⁽⁴⁶⁾ is an influencer marketing tool that helps you find influencers on TikTok, Instagram, YouTube and Twitch. The software lets you filter influencers and check profile analytics for every social network individually. You can also use the fraud detection feature to avoid fake influencers.

Lloyd Griffith 📍 ⚠️ Comedy Television and film ✉️ ⋮ + ADD TO

Lloyd Griffith is an English comedian, actor, presenter and singer from Grimsby, England, and was a presenter on Sky Sports show Soccer AM until the end of the 2018-2019 season.

📍 United Kingdom
Male • 38
English

📌 Sports Television and film Soccer Travel destinations
Style and fashion

246.2K CONNECTIONS

- 📷 lloydgriffith 112.8K
- 📺 Lloyd Griffith 60.2K
- 🐦 LloydGriffith 49.3K
- 📘 lloydgriffithcomedian 23.9K
- +1

RECENT POSTS KEY METRICS AUDIENCE SIMILAR CREATORS >>

📷 lloydgriffith ACTIVE AUDIENCE: 82% 🔄 UPDATE 📄 FULL AUDIENCE DATA

Gender

- MALE: 85.0%
- FEMALE: 15.0%

Age

- < 18: 6.3%
- 18-24: 37.3%
- 25-34: 36.2%
- 35-44: 15.3%
- 45-64: 4.9%
- >64: <0.05%

Top Countries

- 🇬🇧 United Kingdom: 75.1%
- 🇺🇸 United States: 4.2%
- 🇮🇪 Ireland: 2.9%
- 🇪🇸 Spain: 2.3%
- 🇦🇺 Australia: 1.9%

Influencer marketing tools for outreach

NinjaOutreach: NinjaOutreach⁽⁴⁷⁾ is a popular influencer outreach tool that lets you find email addresses, social profiles, and more in any location or niche. You can also schedule emails and follow-ups, keep track of conversations and manage influencer relationships through the platform.

📧 Lists 🔍 Search 📄 Templates 📧 Inbox 🔄 Active Campaigns Schedule A Campaign 🔔 🌐

Select a List Select Email Select Template

Other (optional):
Relationships Tags

1. How many emails do you want to send per day?
⏪ 200 ⏩

2. Set up your schedule
 Send Now Send Later

3. Add email follow ups (optional) ⓘ
Select Template Send after 'N'...
Select Template Send after 'N'...

Note: If you're using a Send As alias in Gmail make sure you are forwarding incoming emails to your connected Gmail account so we can deactivate follow ups for replies.

4. Filter your list of leads (optional)
 Check Leads 🔗

Campaign 1 📄

🚀 Launch Campaign 📧 7

Influencer marketing tools for management

Upfluence: Upfluence⁽⁴⁸⁾ is a one-stop influencer management solution that provides influencer identification, analysis, campaign management, product seeding, affiliate management, and various other services. You can also manage influencer payments from within the platform.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Influencer	Lists	Real Audience Instagram	Email	Sort	
<input type="checkbox"/>	CYPPE	Paris 2019 +2 more	88% Real	jamesdouw@gmail.com	A → Z	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cesar Bertrand	Travel 2019 +2 more	92% Real	business@cires.com	Z → A	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Pierre Erati	Inf - Paris - 2018	98% Real	meliana829@me.com	Display	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Anil	Tourism Maroc - IG	66% Real	meliana829@me.com	With an email	
<input type="checkbox"/>	TalesTech	Paris - 2019 +3 more	91% Real	catalina@live.com	Without an email	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Donovan Henri	France Travel +6 more	99% Real	lilitrello@gmail.com	Search	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Primadonna	Air France +1 more	96% Real	primadonna19@me.com	Remove field	
<input type="checkbox"/>	Nathan Martinez	France 2019 +1 more	60% Real	tropical@eliana.com	Clear filters	
					300k	300k
					133k	133k
					135k	135k
					142k	142k
					182k	182k

Marketplace influencer marketing tools

Collabstr: Collabstr⁽⁴⁹⁾ is an influencer marketplace specialising in Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. You can purchase pre-packaged services from influencers in various niches and locations. It's a quick and easy way to create viral content for your brand.

Find and Hire Influencers in Seconds

Find Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube influencers to create unique content for your brand

Platform

Choose a platform

Category

Enter keywords, niches or categories

Featured

Hire top influencers across all platforms

See All

TikTok
Travel & Lifestyle Content Creator

\$250

Instagram
South Asian Fashion, Beauty, Lifestyle & Home

\$750

Instagram
Lifestyle Content Creator

\$589

TikTok
Music Niche Content Creator

\$700

How to measure campaign success

Establishing and measuring the success of a marketing campaign involves using KPIs. Here is a list⁽⁵⁰⁾ of 21 KPIs that can help you measure the success of any campaign:

- **Return on investment (ROI)**
- **Cost per win**
- **Cost per lead**
- **Cost per conversion**
- **Customer lifetime value**
- **Cost per acquisition**
- **Conversion rate**
- **Website traffic**
- **Traffic by source**
- **New versus returning visitors**
- **Sessions**
- **Average session duration**
- **Bounce rate**
- **Exit rate**
- **Page views**
- **Impressions**
- **Social reach**
- **Social engagement**
- **Email open rate**
- **Click-through rate (CTR)**
- **Cost per click**

Measuring the success of a marketing campaign factors in many of the metrics mentioned above and requires a plan to best determine what KPIs apply to what you're measuring.

Create a goal to achieve

A marketing campaign strategy begins by setting a goal to measure with initial metrics to compare. Consider using the SMART⁽⁵¹⁾ goal technique:

Specific: Give a clear and detailed description of what you need to achieve.

Measurable: Include metrics and target numbers that show success.

Achievable: Ensure your goal is challenging but realistic enough to reach.

Relevant: Make sure the goal you set is relevant to the company's overarching objectives.

Time-bound: Set milestones and dates to meet your goal.

Set a firm time frame

Establishing a solid time frame⁽⁵²⁾, whether 14 days or 14 months, provides the parameters around which to measure your success and helps create a sense of urgency. Time frames allow you to make year-over-year or month-over-month comparisons to track and measure data.

Select success factors

Select which success factors⁽⁵³⁾ you want to measure for your marketing campaigns, such as sales, new users, social impressions, newsletter sign-ups or loyalty purchases. Outlining specific and quantifiable results helps you measure success later. Here are a few examples of goals that involve specific, measurable factors:

- Gain 100,000 social media impressions within the first week of the marketing campaign.
- Secure sales from 15% of the loyal customer base.
- Drive traffic to the company's website with the goal of 10,000 views per day.

Give specific details

Providing as much detail as possible around your KPIs helps teams know what to focus on and how to achieve the goal you set. For example, "Grow target audience followers" is vague and doesn't explain what to measure specifically. In comparison, "Grow target audience followers on all four social media channels by 30% within three months" includes more details⁽⁵⁴⁾ to explain the goal in a more specific way.

Draft a marketing measurement template

Once you decide which metrics match the goal of your marketing campaign and what time frame you want to measure the results within, consider creating a template⁽⁵⁵⁾ with all of the KPIs you intend to track and measure. Include items like:

- Initial goals
- Time frames for the marketing campaign
- KPI metrics at the beginning, middle and end of the campaign or other milestones
- Expectations or known potential issues
- What worked well and what didn't
- A summary of any unplanned events or effects

Ethics and transparency

A major aspect of influencer marketing is ethics and transparency since these are the elements that build up trust between the influencer and their audience⁽⁵⁶⁾. One ethical principle in influencer marketing is to reveal partnerships and sponsorships with clarity. The audience has a right to know if influencers are being paid for advertising any product or service. It is vital for influencers to use hashtags like #ad, #sponsored, or #paidpartnership in order to signal when content has been sponsored⁽⁵⁷⁾. Through this openness, viewers can assess the genuineness as well as the believability of the material they watch or read based on facts.

Authenticity⁽⁵⁸⁾ plays a significant role in influencer marketing, especially when it comes to disclosing partnerships. While creating promotional content, influencers should focus on recommendations that are truthful and can be related to their own personal brands and values. A higher level of trust is more likely to be established between influencers and their audiences if the former adopt an attitude of being honest and genuine throughout their work. In such a manner, influencers ought to promote products or services that they trust⁽⁵⁹⁾, as well as those that appeal to their followers. Authenticity establishes credibility and nurtures enduring relationships with the fan base, hence enhancing successful influencer marketing.

Transparency should be one of the qualities and merits possessed by an influencer when advertising a product or service. This would involve portraying the exact facts, properties, as well as setting distinct boundaries between personal opinions and true information⁽⁶⁰⁾. Making misleading or false representations of products discourages trustworthiness and harms the reliability of the use of influencer marketing on a general scale. It is thus mandatory that influencers guarantee their contents are always honest, precise, and transparent so that they don't lose faith with their audience⁽⁶¹⁾. Engaging with audiences in a responsible way includes obtaining consent from people featured in posts and following data protection laws while using personal information of followers. Acknowledging privacy rights is one such instance that indicates ethical behaviour and fosters trust among recipients.

An important step for influencers is to study advertising regulations⁽⁶²⁾ and laws that are applied in their regions and keep their content compliant with these laws. This means not only obeying the requirements for disclosure, truthfulness, and fairness in advertising imposed by regulatory bodies such as the Federal Trade Commission (FTC)⁽⁶³⁾ in the USA or the Advertising Standards Authority (ASA)⁽⁶⁴⁾ in the UK but also following the guidelines and recommendations to protect the rights of consumers of a similar type. In turn, regulation-abiding conduct by influencers will bring influencer marketing to an ethically higher level, thus benefiting this kind of advertising as well as advertisers and consumers.

The future of nanoinfluencers

Emerging trends

Changing trends in this industry can make or break your business. It's crucial to stay up to date with these trends to stay ahead of your competitors. Let's explore the trends that will help you to maintain an edge in this industry.

Influx of nano and microinfluencers

If you are a brand invested in Influencer marketing, you would know that recent years have seen a seismic shift towards nano and micro-influencers⁽⁶⁵⁾. One possible reason for this could be a smaller yet highly engaged audience, which helps cultivate a strong community. Micro-influencers are the largest group among all tiers of influencers comprising around 47.3% which makes it the ideal group to reach the desired audience. You will be surprised to know that the average engagement rate of a micro-influencer is 6% which is higher as compared to the engagement rate of a macro influencer which is 4.8%. This might help you make good choices for your brand!

AI integration

Artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming a prominent part of Influencer Marketing in today's world⁽⁶⁶⁾. It is revolutionising the industry by shaping it into a performance-driven venture. It has made Influencer marketing easier for the brands by helping them find the correct influencer that aligns with their messaging. Here are a few other key areas where AI is helping brands in solving complex problems like analysing vast data and bridging the gap between the perfect creator and the brand:

- a) Easier Discovery Process: With AI tools that analyse vast data, brands can now identify the most relevant influencers for their campaign based on data that is not just the follower count⁽⁶⁷⁾. AI tools not only help the brands discover the desired influencer, but also help delve deeper into the metrics of the influencer, such as engagement rate, audience demographics, authenticity, audience relevance and much more. You can now understand how AI makes discovery an easy process for brands.
- b) Campaign Performance Forecasting: AI-enhanced tools help marketers predict the future of their campaigns and optimise their strategies with unprecedented accuracy⁽⁶⁸⁾. AI-enhanced tools identify and analyse historical data and real time trends which helps forecast the future of the campaign. And that's not all, these tools are capable enough to analyse campaign performance in real-time, helping brands achieve maximum ROI.
- c) Fraud detection: Influencer fraud is detected as a common issue these days⁽⁶⁹⁾. The AI-enhanced tools help the brands focus on analysing patterns that humans might miss ensuring that the brands do not have to deal with influencers that have fake followings.
- d) Brands implementing AI: By leveraging AI algorithms to analyse audience demographics, engagement metrics and content preferences, Bacardi successfully targeted niche audiences and boosted brand awareness using 'THE CONCEPT A.I.BUM': the first AI powered EP produced by Grammy winner BOI-1DA⁽⁷¹⁾.

Building Trust and Relationships

This year brands will move their focus towards long-term partnerships rather than project-based partnerships with the influencers⁽⁷¹⁾. This will help brands build a more sustainable relationship with their audiences. Influencers will also get the opportunity to thoroughly understand the brand values, enabling them to authentically incorporate these values into the content they share on social media. This will help them resonate with their audiences more effectively eventually fostering a stronger affinity of their followers towards the brand.

Increased TikTok growth

TikTok is one of the fastest-growing platforms for influencer marketing. The projected budget for TikTok Influencer Marketing in the year 2024 is estimated to be \$1.32 billion⁽⁷²⁾. This is almost 10 times higher than the year 2020. The diverse user base makes TikTok a great platform for brand discovery and advertising.

Rise of Short-form Video Content

Short-form video content isn't going anywhere anytime soon⁽⁷³⁾. In the realm of short-form video content, TikTok once reigned supreme as the pioneer. However, now we witness the evolution of platforms like Instagram and YouTube, as they introduce Reels and YouTube Shorts, thereby solidifying their presence in this space.

Influencers and brands should therefore focus on creating impactful content in a snackable short format. The first few seconds are crucial to grab the user's attention to the video to deliver the message by the end of the video. It's all about being able to deliver your message effectively using bite-sized pieces.

Authentic influencing

This significant trend in influencer marketing focuses on the importance of authenticity and transparency in the partnership of influencers and brands⁽⁷⁴⁾. Audiences expect the influencers to tell their first-hand experiences that the audience can relate to which helps them build an authentic connection to the person or the brand they follow. A growing trend has been observed among Gen Z and nano content creators where they prioritise genuine content that resonates with their audiences.

Live shopping

Live shopping has increased in recent years and this is not going to change in 2024 too⁽⁷⁵⁾. Live shopping, where influencers sell products through live video on social media has become a preferred way to shop by the users. This strategy helps a brand to engage with its customers in real-time through live sessions on social media platforms. It allows brands to showcase their products directly to the consumers and leverage the influencers to drive sales.

Companies like Amazon, Myntra and Flipkart have leveraged this strategy in India to entice users to directly shop from live videos. Amazon Live aims to infuse trust among new shoppers though by using local influencers. Amazon India onboarded 300 influencers to host over 1000 live streams over 8 weeks to make the "Great Indian Festival" a success. This market is expected to reach \$120 billion by the year 2026 and aspires to become the world's second-largest e-commerce industry⁽⁷⁶⁾.

Predictions for nanoinfluencers

A new era for micro-influencers emerges

In the 2024 creator economy, the resurgence of micro and nano influencers is on the horizon. Small and medium-sized businesses are prioritising micro-creators, but why? Mostly, micro-creators are becoming crucial for brands as they help maximise impact on social media without breaking the bank⁽⁷⁷⁾.

Specialised and niche influencers will take centre stage

As social media becomes saturated with influencers, the need to carve out a unique niche and value proposition becomes paramount⁽⁷⁸⁾. For influencers, the key to success lies in standing out, catching a brand's eye, and increasing the likelihood of collaborating on impactful campaigns. Recognizing the importance of specialisation, creators are choosing to delve further into their niche fields or refine their creation styles.

AI to play a more significant role in content creation

The emerging influence of AI technology is reshaping the creator economy, and 2024 is poised to fully embrace its potential⁽⁷⁹⁾. No longer a futuristic concept, AI is now a transformative force across various industries, including marketing and content creation. Its impact on enhancing marketing and creative performance, efficiency, and innovation is significant, mainly achieved through automation and data analysis.

Long-form video content will resurge

In the realm of social media, short-form videos have long claimed the spotlight, dominating platforms like TikTok, Instagram Reels, and YouTube Shorts. These bite-sized videos have transformed the way we consume content⁽⁸⁰⁾. Yet the question arises: is long-form video content facing extinction? Not quite.

Surprisingly, 59% of Gen Z turn to short-form video apps to discover things that they later watch longer versions of⁽⁸¹⁾.

Brace for a notable surge in cross-promotion opportunities

Amidst the surge in social media usage, especially among Gen Z audiences, the inclination to explore alternatives to Google search intensifies due to concerns about declining search quality⁽⁸²⁾. TikTok and Instagram emerge as the preferred choices, marking a significant shift away from traditional search engines.

In light of this, creators are strategically redirecting their focus. Rather than delving into the complexities of Google's algorithms, they are opting to diversify their traffic sources⁽⁸³⁾. The key lies in building a robust and authentic brand presence across multiple platforms.

The creator economy will solidify as a viable career path

As of 2024, the creator economy is stepping into the academic spotlight, shedding its image as a side effect of social media growth. It's becoming a legitimate career choice with abundant options⁽⁸⁴⁾, and this shift is especially exciting for the 54% of young adults keen on diving into content creation⁽⁸⁵⁾, aligning seamlessly with Gen Z's desire for career independence.

Final conclusions

Nanoinfluencers are a unique group of influencers with a smaller yet highly committed following. These people usually have about 1,000 to 10,000 followers and often have specialised knowledge or interests that give them substantial influence among specific communities. Nanoinfluencers stand out because they are authentic, relatable, and can create strong bonds with their audience. In contrast to macro and microinfluencers, quality plays a bigger role for nanoinfluencers than quantity, leading to greater engagement and trust levels.

Although nanoinfluencers have a smaller outreach than other influencers, their effect on purchasing behaviour and brand evaluation cannot be underestimated. Nanoinfluencers who lack knowledge about the subject matter cannot have influence because their content lacks authenticity. The person behind this profile is viewed as more reliable and trustworthy if the opinions are stated by a nanoinfluencer. The targeted market audience also ensures that such brands can reach highly interested people, thus making them buy. Working with nano-influencers also provides increased credibility and greater authenticity in marketing endeavours.

One of the essential things a brand needs to consider is the authenticity, transparency, and respect that should be prioritised when working with nanoinfluencers. Without building authentic relationships between brands and influencers on common shared values and goals, influencer marketing campaigns will fail to succeed. It is important for brands to give nano-influencers a chance to create content that is based on their personal identity and to which they feel connected to their viewers. More than this, trust and credibility are closely tied to the ways you communicate, including honesty about paid posts and sponsorship deals.

From a forward-thinking perspective, it is evident that the future of nanoinfluencers is bright, as brands continue to appreciate the importance of authenticity and community-based marketing strategies. Nanoinfluencers are believed to be an increasingly important part of influencer marketing campaigns, especially due to the efforts by brands in reaching highly targeted and niche markets. The establishment and subsequent growth of social media platforms such as TikTok, which encourage authentic content creation, further affirm nanoinfluencers' relevance in influencing consumer trends and preferences. With the perpetually changing landscape in influencer marketing, nanoinfluencers are anticipated to stay relevant in driving engagements, establishing brand loyalty, and playing a role in shaping the digital market space.

Thanks for reading.

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Presentation:

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